

Kinetics of thermal decomposition of synthetic hydrogel of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ system : Effect of composition

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Abstract : Different molar ratio of zirconia : mullite precursors have been derived by adjusting the composition of mixed hydroxides hydrogel in $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ system. Kinetics of multistage thermal dehydration of such co-precipitated hydrogels has been studied in relation to composition of as prepared gel under isothermal conditions. The importance of the compositional effect on the kinetics of thermal decomposition of multi-component hydrogels is apparent from the variation of extent of validity of the first order law, values of rate constants and activation energies at the initial and final stages of dehydration reaction.

Keywords : Kinetics, thermal dehydration, composition, zirconia-mullite hydrogels.

Introduction

In recent times sol-gel method appears extremely advantageous for the synthesis of microfine reactive powder particularly in the multi component ceramic system which allows manipulation of green microstructure with controlled morphology, high purity and better homogeneity of precursor powders. The ternary $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ system provides tremendous scope of deriving ZrO_2 -mullite based composite precursors with varying ZrO_2 content which has secured extensive applications as toughened structural and engineering materials, excellent corrosion resistant refractories, catalyst carriers, ceramic membranes, coatings on piezoelectric components and ceramic sensors.

Bradecki *et al.* followed the solid state sintering technique for development of zirconia-mullite composites. The sintering of both materials undergoes a series of step : decomposition of zircon in the surrounding of alumina forms zirconia and amorphous silica, and then amorphous silica reacts with alumina to form mullite. However the dissolution of alumina and diffusion of Al^{3+} with in silica is a slowest rate than the decomposition of zircon¹.

Park and co-workers prepared zirconia-mullite composites by an infiltration route which incorporates ZrO_2 into mullite by infiltrating partially reaction sintered mul-

lite compacts by interaction with $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ solutions².

However, main drawbacks of solid state sintering using mixture of pure oxide components include requirement of higher sintering temperature, inhomogeneity, lack of stoichiometry crystallographic nature and micro structural features.

Different techniques of multi component ZrO_2 -mullite precursor synthesis such as co-precipitation, sol-gel, hydrothermal, combustion etc. are focused³⁻¹¹. In earlier communication, the synthesis of mixed hydroxides hydrogel at a fixed molar ratio for ZrO_2 : mullite has been highlighted⁹.

In this communication, the kinetics of thermal dehydration of co-precipitated zirconia-mullite hydrogel in relation to variation of molar ratio for zirconia and mullite has been investigated.

Experimental

The synthesis of zirconia-mullite gels were carried out by aqueous phase interaction of requisite amount of 0.2 M solution of A.R. grade $Al(NO_3)_3$, 0.2 M solution of A.R. grade $ZrOCl_2$ with silicic acid sol and then raising the pH of mixed salts solution to 9.0 by addition of 1 : 3 NH_3 solution as basic media. In each case, molar ratio of Al_2O_3 : SiO_2 was kept constant corresponding to

the composition of mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) but the molar ratio of zirconia : mullite varied. The sillicic acid sol was prepared by passing slowly 2.0% sodium silicate aqueous solution of 1 : 2 molar ratio through a column of Dowex-50 cation exchanger repeatedly. The mixed hydroxides gel of zirconia-alumina-silica was washed thoroughly with hot water to remove different impurities and finally vacuum dried at 60°C . A Hitachi Infrared spectrophotometer (model No. 270-30) was used for IR analysis of the dried precursor. The specific surface area of the powder was measured with an instrument Carle Erba Strumentazione, Italy based on nitrogen adsorption BET principle. The thermal dehydration of dried precursors was investigated under similar isothermal conditions¹⁴.

Results and discussion

Physico-chemical characteristics of synthesized mixed layered hydroxides hydrogel were given in Table 1. Chemical analysis of the precursors did not differ to the batches taken, indicating total interaction of the ingredi-

($160\text{--}180^\circ\text{C}$) for dehydration of zirconium hydroxide and 3rd one (280°C) due to aluminium hydroxide. Though there was no significant change in the peak temperature with variation of composition but with increase in the proportion of ZrO_2 , the peaks shifted towards right hand side. This is attributed that orientation of water molecules in a particular hydroxide may be influenced by the neighboring hydroxide. The kinetic parameters were drawn by applying Guggenheim equation¹⁴.

$$\log \Delta L = -K_1 t / 2.303 + \log [L_\infty \{1 - \exp(K_1 \Delta t)\}]$$

The reaction rate constants (K_1) and the equilibrium weight losses (L_∞) were calculated. In the above equation ΔL is the difference between the weight loss at time $t + \Delta t$ and at time t . The time interval Δt between two sets of readings has been kept constants at values greater than twice the time for 50% dehydration.

With the variation of molar ratio of the ingredients, the nature of the rate curves did not differ and the calculated results are given in Table 2. In the multistage dehy-

Table 1. Physico-chemical characteristics of the synthesized mixed hydrogels

Batch No.	Molar ratio of $\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{SiO}_2$	Empirical formula	DTGA peak temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Surface area ($\text{m}^2 \text{gm}^{-1}$)
I	$\text{ZrO}_2 \cdot 1.3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 0.86\text{SiO}_2$	$0.463\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{mullite}$	100, 160, 280	194.6
II	$\text{ZrO}_2 \cdot 0.86\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 0.57\text{SiO}_2$	$0.699\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{mullite}$	80, 160, 280	201.5
III	$\text{ZrO}_2 \cdot 0.57\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 0.38\text{SiO}_2$	$1.05\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{mullite}$	100, 180, 280	205.6

ents in the aqueous phase with respect to mixed hydroxides formation and complete precipitation of the same.

Dry powders had significantly high surface areas proportional to the ZrO_2 content of the mixture. This indicated the finer particle size of $\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_4$ precipitates.

The IR spectra of all the samples (Fig. 1) exhibited O-H stretching vibration in the region $3472\text{--}3484 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ bonded to the surface of the molecule. The vibrational frequency was maximum for batch III and minimum for batch II which was related to the stronger bonds between water molecules in the later case. Again, all the samples exhibited the same strong absorption band at 1386 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of $-\text{Al}=\text{O}$ bonds in the mixed precursors^{12,13}.

In the differential thermo gravimetric analysis (Fig. 2) three peaks corresponding to the dehydration of individual hydroxide were observed. 1st peak ($80\text{--}100^\circ\text{C}$) was related to dehydration of sillicic acid, 2nd one

dration process, rate study was conducted at each peak temperature.

In the initial stage of dehydration, which followed first order kinetics, the reaction rate constants exhibited true endothermic nature and compositional effect was not much significant. The values of the rate constants increased with the increase in temperature in each case. Again in each composition, the magnitude of K_1 was maximum with the second peak compared to the others, although the temperature effect was different.

From the Figs. 5, 6 and 7 it is evident that batch II composition exhibited highest value of rate constant throughout the temperature range for the 1st peak, although the rate of decomposition of all the three batches becomes equal at about 120°C . In case of 2nd peak, batch II showed maximum K_1 values again in comparison to batch I and batch III in the temperature range of $140\text{--}220^\circ\text{C}$. In case of 3rd peak, batch I was found to yield maximum K_1 value in the temperature range used

Fig. 1. IR spectrogram of the $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogels

Fig. 2. DTGA curve of the $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogels.

Table 2. Values of rate constants (K_1), equilibrium weight losses (L_{∞}) from log ΔL vs time plots and extent of validity of first order law and rate constant (K_2) at final stage

Batch No.	Peak	Temp. (°C)	K_1 per min	L_{∞} value (gms)	Validity of first order law (%)	K_2 per min
I	1st peak	60	0.011	0.062	35.81	0.014
		80	0.028	0.113	70.22	0.028
		100	0.039	0.134	74.18	0.052
	2nd Peak	120	0.049	0.284	78.87	0.077
		140	0.060	0.053	49.12	0.002
		160	0.083	0.093	82.34	0.007
		180	0.187	0.102	86.18	0.012
		200	0.242	0.493	86.98	0.017
		220	0.282	0.582	89.91	0.021
		240	0.024	0.094	65.38	0.009
	3rd Peak	260	0.082	0.113	81.12	0.013
		280	0.113	0.188	85.41	0.015
		300	0.142	0.382	86.38	0.018
		320	0.192	0.577	89.15	0.019
		320	0.192	0.577	89.15	0.019
II	1st peak	60	0.018	0.041	31.27	0.019
		80	0.029	0.127	72.15	0.030
		100	0.042	0.192	76.22	0.054
		120	0.047	0.354	76.73	0.069
	2nd Peak	140	0.071	0.062	55.29	0.007
		160	0.094	0.098	83.33	0.013
		180	0.163	0.112	85.27	0.019
		200	0.273	0.344	87.18	0.032
		220	0.392	0.511	88.19	0.033
		240	0.025	0.093	70.11	0.009
	3rd Peak	260	0.092	0.102	84.48	0.012
		280	0.102	0.158	86.61	0.012
		300	0.133	0.413	86.93	0.013
		320	0.192	0.553	89.54	0.013
		320	0.192	0.553	89.54	0.013
III	1st peak	60	0.012	0.029	34.32	0.015
		80	0.028	0.104	31.88	0.028
		100	0.040	0.181	73.22	0.066
		120	0.048	0.375	77.91	0.084
	2nd peak	140	0.005	0.044	51.15	0.003
		160	0.092	0.142	81.77	0.007
		180	0.144	0.144	73.21	0.013
		200	0.23	0.586	83.32	0.019
		220	0.252	0.611	88.18	0.02
		240	0.024	0.066	64.41	0.007
	3rd Peak	260	0.065	0.213	87.11	0.007
		280	0.092	0.214	87.11	0.007
		300	0.132	0.421	88.32	0.011
		320	0.173	0.631	88.35	0.012
		320	0.173	0.631	88.35	0.012

Fig. 3. $\log \Delta L$ vs time plots during dehydration of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogels for the 2nd peak.

Table 3. Activation energy calculated from Arrhenius plot at initial and final stage of dehydration for different peak temperatures

Batch No.	Activated energy at initial stage E_1			Activated energy at final stage E_2		
	(kcal mol ⁻¹) for			(kcal mol ⁻¹) for		
	1st peak	2nd peak	3rd peak	1st peak	2nd peak	3rd peak
I	5.17	8.253	20.613	7.181	9.157	8.456
II	4.82	7.776	18.642	8.416	11.151	7.241
III	3.83	4.896	18.59	9.152	10.23	5.828

(240–320°C). It clearly revealed that the initial dehydration reaction with 1st order mechanism, rate constant showed an ascending order for all the peaks in the temperature range used.

The equilibrium dehydration (L_∞) followed a direct relationship with the peak temperature in each composition. L_∞ was minimum during dehydration at the region of the first peak. The difference in the magnitude of L_∞ between second and third peak was not significant.

In each case, the reaction rate constants related to the dehydration of the hydrogel increased from the first peak to the second. But due to the reduced concentration of the water molecules and contraction of the gel structure, the rate of expulsion again decreased which was observed at the region of the third peak. The importance of compositional effect of the hydrogel was apparent from the extent of validity of first order kinetics where a positive relationship was noted with the temperature of the peak.

Fig. 4. Arrhenius plot of $\log K_1$ vs $1/T \times 10^3$ for the 2nd peak.

Fig. 5. K_1 value vs temperature plots during dehydration of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogel for 1st peak.

Fig. 6. K_1 value vs temperature plots during dehydration of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogel for 2nd peak.

Fig. 7. K_1 value vs temperature plots during dehydration of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogel for 3rd peak.

The extent of validity of first order kinetics was directly proportional to the temperature of the heat treatment and about 78% of the dehydration reaction followed first order law for first peak while about 89% dehydration followed first order law for both the 2nd and 3rd peak.

The complete dehydration reaction of the compositions did not follow first order kinetics. The rate constants at the final stage reaction (K_2) was calculated from the slope of the curves (Figs. 3 and 4) at the point of

termination of the first order kinetics, using relation :

$$K_2 = \frac{dl/dt}{L_\infty - L}$$

where, dl/dt was the slope of the weight loss vs time curves at the point of dehydration beyond which first order kinetics were not followed. True endothermic nature was observed in both stages of dehydration. For 2nd and 3rd peak, K_2 values were always lower than the corresponding K_1 values which might be attributed to the

decrease in concentration of water molecules, increase in the diffusion path and decrease in the vapor pressure of the formed steam.

Figs. 8, 9 and 10 demonstrated that K_2 value for 1st peak was highest in batch III, while for 2nd peak K_2 was highest in batch II and for 3rd peak batch I have the highest value on above temperature range examined. This indicated that with increase of ZrO_2 content in the ZrO_2

: mullite precursors, the rate of final stage dehydration (K_2) steadily increases in the temperature range examined via 2nd order mechanism.

At the first peak temperature, which was due to dehydration of sillicic acid, K_2 values was higher than the corresponding K_1 values whereas at the other temperatures reverse relationship was noticed. This might be due

Fig. 8. K_2 value vs temperature plots during dehydration of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogel for 1st peak.

Fig. 9. K_2 value vs temperature plots during dehydration of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogel for 2nd peak.

Fig. 10. K_2 value vs temperature plots during dehydration of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ hydrogel for 3rd peak.

to the fact that in the low temperature dehydration, gel structure was not destroyed and due to the presence of significant water molecules, the interaction of the escaping water molecules with the hydrophilic surface was minimum.

With the increase of ZrO_2 content in the composition, the activation energy (E_1) was calculated from Arrhenius plots which were observed to decrease steadily at the initial stage of dehydration for any peak. Some anomalies were noticed in E_2 values. For the 3rd peak, the activation energy was always lower at the later stage of dehydration irrespective of the composition of the hydrogel. This indicated a reduction in the diffusion path for the loss of water molecules due to larger contraction of the gel structure before complete collapse.

Conclusions :

(i) Hydrogels of the desired molar ratios of $ZrO_2-Al_2O_3-SiO_2$ system can be prepared by the solution-precipitation technique from their mixed salts solution.

(ii) Although the general kinetic nature of the multi-stage dehydration process of zirconia-mullite precursors remains independent of composition of the co-precipitated gels, their kinetic parameters appear strongly influenced by composition in relation to ZrO_2 content.

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